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Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication II

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Introduction

The COEVOLVERS project Strategy and Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC Plan), is a tool for helping consortium partners achieve the project's general goal: "to contribute to the societal change urgently needed to address the ongoing biodiversity and climate crises and to develop a sense of belonging and committed action for nature". A further aim is "to engage & motivate decision- and policymakers to ensure their contribution to transformational impacts at a local, national and EU level". The document referred to above was developed in M6, and this document is an update.

This deliverable has been developed by ESSRG, leader of WP6 (the WP responsible for communication and dissemination), with input from all project partners, as part of Task 6.3 by reflecting on the past 17 months of the project and reviewing the project's DEC Plan (D.6.1).

WP6 asked all partners to complete a questionnaire (see Annex) and organised and facilitated a communication and dissemination workshop in M17 to develop new tools, strategic steps, and plans for all partners' communication and dissemination activities. We started to examine and work on the exploitation activities in more depth at the annual consortium meeting in M18 where a list of results and possible key exploitable results will be made.

The deliverable will be further updated in M38, as D.6.3 Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication III.

Some partners have decided on or are planning new communication tools or activities based on their experiences since the project started. Partners also managed to segment their audiences further (since the Audience Segmentation Workshop at the project's kick-off meeting), which will ensure the development of tailor-made communication and dissemination tools and activities.

New tools for communication

A [project overview](#) has been prepared and designed and is available from the [About subpage](#) of the project website. A printable version was also developed that can be used as a leaflet. Based on the project overview, each Living Lab received a version with a general introduction and a description that contains only the presentation of their own Living Labs. The document contains general information on the project's goals, challenges, possible solutions, the list of partners, funding information, and activities of the Living Labs. Partners use the leaflet and the project overview to communicate about the project at different events (e.g. conferences, cluster meetings.)

A new subpage has been added to the website for blog posts (under <https://co-evolvers.eu/news>), as requested by project partners. A guideline on how to write blog posts has been compiled by WP6 and sent to partners.

A communication and dissemination workshop was held online in March 2023 to support partners in designing their communications activities for the forthcoming 12 months, namely, what to communicate, where, and how.

A mentimeter output from the communication and dissemination workshop

The Strategy and Plan for DEC mentioned using Google Analytics to track website visitor data. However, the use of Google Analytics was stopped after 3 weeks of use following the request of the Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke, the coordinator). Under data protection legislation, Luke has discontinued the use of the Google Analytics tool on their websites in the spring 2023. The reason is that Google Analytics is not reporting visitor analytics in a way that ensures customer privacy. Instead, the project has changed to using Matomo Analytics, as recommended by the consortium leader institution, LUKE. Matomo Analytics was installed on the Coevolvers website in November 2023.

As for social media, our focus of communication has shifted from X (previously named Twitter) towards LinkedIn because many followers of former Twitter left the platform due to the changes in the new management set-up of X in late 2022 and early 2023. We continue to post about Living Lab activities, publications, workshops and conferences, and all project-related news on both channels. More and more project outcomes will probably be produced that will be worth posting in thematic LinkedIn groups as well.

Children's personal data: Children merit specific protection on the internet as they are less aware of the risks and the consequences of being present on public platforms. As some Living Labs are connected to schools and families with children, we agreed to avoid using photos that show children's faces to ensure that children are not recognisable on photos publicly used in our project, even if the parent or the child's legal guardian has signed a GDPR consent form. (If for some reason this is unavoidable, the photo user will initiate a discussion with DEC WP.)

A model example of a social media picture showing a child

The Hungarian, the Estonian, the Finnish and the Scottish Living Labs created newsletters or email groups to inform their communities, stakeholders, and the members of the National Consultation Groups about what is happening in the Living Labs. These newsletters are not public; only voluntarily subscribed members receive them.

A poster exhibition for lay audiences is also under development by the Finnish Living Lab, as it was realised that nature-based solutions are still unknown to wider audiences. The Scottish Living Lab will create digital stories (video outputs via YouTube) about some of the research activities they conduct in the Living Lab.

The Beskydy Living Lab developed [a platform](#) that is based on the concept of virtual commons and connected to the Facebook account Nase Lesy (Our Forests) for better communication and dissemination of project activities among stakeholders in their local languages. Moreover, the virtual commons in Beskydy aims to co-create a climate-smart common pool resource management regime of water and forest for the cross-border Beskydy community and networking in the online space.

Some Living Labs started public events to raise awareness about the LL among residents and other actors like local enterprises and schools. The Estonian Living Lab has a public event series, and the Finnish Living Lab organised public events to raise awareness of the Living Lab among the residents and other actors (e.g. a film day festival).

There have been changes in the **social media channels** of the partners since M6, when D6.1 was finalised (see p.11-20 in D6.1). We note the changes as follows:

The University of Cagliari's X page was shut down. For COEVOLVERS-related posts, they would like to use in the future the social media channels of the Regional Park where the Living Lab is situated—namely, the Facebook and Instagram pages named "Parco Naturale Regionale Molentargius-Saline" (35,958 followers) and "molentargiussalineofficial" (4,376 followers).

The Scottish Living Lab has developed a LinkedIn page: [Nature-Based Solutions: UK wetlands, forests and parks](#).

The Estonian Living Lab uses the Department of Semiotics' Facebook page to create and promote events within various social media groups. The bio- and eco-semiotics work group of the University of Tartu has a webpage that can also promote project-related content, especially [the subpage](#) dedicated to the CEOVOLVERS Living Lab.

New tools for dissemination

The [Zenodo account](#) of the project was set up in M9. We use the Zenodo platform to archive and disseminate outcomes, results, and publications related to our project, including blogs and peer-reviewed articles, as well as other research outputs primarily associated with work package activities and knowledge outputs from our Living Labs. Zenodo is part of the OpenAIRE project and is committed to the open access and open data movements in Europe, commissioned by the European Commission.

The Hungarian Living Lab started to build strong connections with the therapists of the hospital where the healing garden is situated. The plan is to include certain COEVOLVERS Living Lab practices and results in some of the therapies.

The Czech-Slovak Living Lab adapted the role board game for elementary school children located in Beskydy Living Lab.

Exploitation

WP6 started to work on the exploitation strategy of the project by the end of the first project year after partners planned in detail their activities for the project's lifetime and beyond. WP6 started to actively involve partners in the exploitation tasks at the annual project meeting in M18 where an exploitation workshop was organised. The goal of this workshop was to develop a common understanding of exploitation (that is in line with the Grant Agreement and Regulation 2021/695) and build a list of project results that will be the basis of the key exploitable results and the results ownership list (including the intellectual property rights protection).

Reporting and monitoring

Each partner and Living Lab has started completing the online Communication Calendar, where they record planned communication and dissemination activities like blog posts, events, presentations, conference papers, local media articles, policy briefs, newsletters, publications, etc.

Partners should report about their DEC activities regularly in an online spreadsheet based on the project's Nextcloud account. The spreadsheet contains information on the type of the event, the number of people reached and on the different audiences if data is available. Based on this spreadsheet the KPIs for DEC are being assessed continuously by WP6 and the coordination team.

Annex

The questionnaire each partner and Living Lab responded to in M16.

1. Have you discovered any new communication and dissemination tools you are using or will use compared to the tools listed in the previous DEC Plan? (List from the 1st DEC Plan: video, local media article, blog post, social media post, policy brief, peer-reviewed publication, symposium, presentation for the researcher community, conference poster.) E.g. the Hungarian LL set up a regular newsletter about their LL activities.
2. Have you discovered any new audiences you would like to communicate with about COEVOLVERS compared to the audiences listed in the previous DEC Plan? (List from the 1st DEC Plan: Citizens, vulnerable groups at LLs, local-level organised actors and administrations, policy makers at the local, national and EU levels, wider society, researcher communities.)
3. Is there any new channel that you use or will surely use compared to the channels listed in the previous DEC Plan? Please, check D6.1, pp.12–20 where all public online channels of each partner are listed, and also think of any other channels that are not listed there but you are using or will use during the project lifetime.
4. Are there any new activities you will do other than the activities listed in the previous DEC Plan? (List from the 1st DEC Plan: Videos, external newsletter entries, local media articles, blogs, news articles, events, policy briefs, peer-reviewed publications, presentations, symposiums, handbook, social media posts.)
5. During the past year, have you discovered any important issues regarding the vulnerability of the LL group you are working with? Is there any sensitive information you weren't aware of before starting working with them within COEVOLVERS? If yes, please list them here.

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